

1 Changes induced by *Trichoderma harzianum* in suppressive compost controlling *Fusarium wilt*

2 Josefa Blaya, Rubén López-Mondéjar, Eva Lloret, Jose Antonio Pascual, Margarita Ros

3 Department of Soil and Water Conservation and Organic Waste Management, Centro de
4 Edafología y Biología Aplicada del Segura (CEBAS-CSIC), Campus de Espinardo, P.O. Box 164,
5 30100 Espinardo, Murcia, Spain

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9

10 Abstract

11 The addition of species of *Trichoderma* to compost is a widespread technique used to control
12 different plant diseases. The biological control activity of these species is mainly attributable to
13 a combination of several mechanisms of action, which may affect the microbiota involved in the
14 suppressiveness of compost. This study was therefore performed to determine the effect of
15 inoculation of *Trichoderma harzianum* (*T. harzianum*) on compost, focusing on bacterial
16 community structure (16S rRNA) and chitinase gene diversity. In addition, the ability of vineyard
17 pruning waste compost, amended (GCTh) or not (GC) with *T. harzianum*, to suppress *Fusarium*
18 wilt was evaluated. The addition of *T. harzianum* resulted in a high relative abundance of certain
19 chitinolytic bacteria as well as in remarkable protection against *Fusarium oxysporum*
20 comparable to that induced by compost GC. Moreover, variations in the abiotic characteristics
21 of the media, such as pH, C, N and iron levels, were observed. Despite the lower diversity of
22 chitinolytic bacteria found in GCTh, the high relative abundance of *Streptomyces* spp. may be
23 involved in the suppressiveness of this growing media. The higher degree of compost
24 suppressiveness achieved after the addition of *T. harzianum* may be due not only to its
25 biocontrol ability, but also to changes promoted in both abiotic and biotic characteristics of the
26 growing media.

27

28 1. Introduction

29 Composting has been widely accepted as one of the most feasible solutions for the treatment
30 and valorization of organic wastes. It has contributed not only to enhancing environmental

31 preservation, but also to the recovery of valuable resources [1]. The use of composts in
32 horticulture and agriculture as growing media can reduce the use of peat, which is a non-
33 renewable resource and conducive to soil borne diseases [2]. Suppressive composts have been
34 commonly used to control plant diseases caused by soil-borne pathogens, such as *Pythium* spp.
35 [3], *Fusarium* spp. [4] or *Phytophthora* spp. [1]. The disease suppression capacity of the compost
36 is attributed to the activities of antagonist microorganisms and related to the stage of
37 composting process [5]. Microbial community surviving the thermophilic phase of composting
38 is not sufficient to support disease, thereby an active and specific microflora adapted to the
39 available substrates following compost maturation or stabilization is essential [5].
40 Recolonization of composts after the heatpeak of the composting process before substantial
41 colonization with mesophilic microorganisms, is the time of inoculation [6] and establishment
42 of biological control agents (BCAs) at high densities to obtain induced suppressive compost [7].
43 Species of the genus *Trichoderma* have been described as potential BCAs due to their high
44 antagonistic ability against several plant fungal pathogens, including *Fusarium* spp.,
45 *Phytophthora* spp., *Sclerotinia* spp., *Rhizoctonia* spp. and *Pythium* spp. [8–10]. Their biological
46 control activity is mainly attributable to a combination of several mechanisms of action, which
47 may include secretion of hydrolytic enzymes, such as chitinases and glucanases, which have
48 been reported to be a key factor in the lysis of cell walls of phytopathogens [11] and anti-
49 microbial compounds [12]. The rapid growth of these species allows them to directly compete
50 for space and nutrients with phytopathogens [9], and indirectly by stimulating plant growth as
51 well as inducing systemic resistance mechanisms in the plant [13]. *Trichoderma* populations can
52 be established relatively easily in different types of soil [14]. Some authors have found that the
53 inoculation of *Trichoderma* only modify slightly the microbial diversity of soils [14,15], while
54 others have showed that the increase of soil microbial biomass after the addition of
55 *Trichoderma*, contributes to a reduction of the biocontrol efficacy of this BCA [16]. However, the
56 effect of inoculated *Trichoderma* on compost have not been deeply studied, and mainly, after
57 the heat peak, when composts show a biological vacuum [4]. *Trichoderma* may induce chemical
58 changes that indirectly exert a control on the dynamics of bacterial community structure.

59 Chitin is the second most abundant natural biopolymer in nature and is widely distributed across
60 diverse environments, comprising structures such as the cell wall of filamentous fungi [17].
61 Chitin degrading enzymes, chitinases, are also found in a wide variety of organisms, including
62 fungi, plants, insects, crustaceans, and bacteria. Chitinases are glycosyl hydrolases that catalyzes
63 the degradation of chitin, a linear β -1, 4-linked polymer of N-acetylglucosamine. Based on amino
64 acid similarity, chitinases are classified into family 18 or 19 of glycosyl hydrolases [18]. The

65 majority of known bacterial chitinases are grouped into family 18 group A [19]. The family 19
66 chitinases are also equally distributed within Streptomyces. The screening of different
67 chitinolytic bacteria community DNA samples may lead to the possible identification of diverse
68 chitinase genes that may have enhanced chitinolytic properties and therefore have potential
69 controlling plant fungal pathogens.

70 The goal of this study was to analyze the influence of the inoculation of *Trichoderma harzianum*
71 on the bacterial community structure and chitinase gene diversity, through 16S rRNA and
72 chitinase gene libraries, of compost against *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* (FOM). Other
73 characteristics of the growing media were also studied.

74

75 **2. Materials and methods**

76 *2.1. Fungal strains and growth conditions*

77 Composts were amended with the BCA *T. harzianum* T-78 (CECT 20714, Spanish Type Culture
78 Collection). The isolate was incubated on potato dextrose agar (PDA, (Sharlau, Spain) 39 g L⁻¹,
79 autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min, and amended with 100 mg L⁻¹ sterilized streptomycin (Sigma,
80 USA) at 28 C for 5 days under no light conditions to obtain active growing microorganisms.
81 Three discs (5 mm) of PDA were suspended in a flask containing 250 ml of potato dextrose broth
82 (PDB, (Sharlau, Spain) 24 g L⁻¹, autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min, and amended with 100 mg L⁻¹
83 sterilized streptomycin) and incubated at 28 C on a rotatory shaker (150 rpm) for 7 days under
84 no light conditions. Conidia were recovered by centrifugation (5000 rpm, 20 min), rinsed twice
85 with sterile distilled water and filtered through 101 quartz wool. The fungus was immobilized in
86 bentonite following the protocol described by Bernal-Vicente [7]. The pathogen FOM was
87 isolated from infected melon plants from a greenhouse nursery. Conidia were recovered as
88 described above for *T. harzianum*.

89 *2.2. Organic amendment*

90 Two green composts containing 100% vineyard pruning wastes were used in this study: green
91 compost (GC) and green compost inoculated at the beginning of the maturation process with *T.*
92 *harzianum* 106 CFU g⁻¹ (GCTh). Composting piles were made in open air piles of 1 m³ as
93 described by Bernal-Vicente [7]. Once the composting process was finished (after 120 days),
94 three samples of each compost pile were taken by mixing nine sub-samples from random sites
95 on each pile. Samples were stored at -20 C for DNA extraction and at 4 C for chemical and
96 microbiological analysis.

97 2.3. Physico–chemical and chemical parameters

98 Compost samples were analyzed for pH and electrical conductivity (EC) in a 1:5 (w/v) water-
99 soluble extract in a conductivimeter and pH-meter (Crison mod. 2001, Barcelona, Spain). Total
100 organic carbon (TOC) was determined by the method of Yeomans and Bremner [20] and total
101 organic nitrogen by the Kjeldahl method as modified by Bremner and Mulvaney [21]. Total P and
102 K were determined in nitric-perchloric digestion extract (1:1), P by colorimetry and K by flame
103 photometry using a Jenway PFP7 flame photometer (Essex, England) [22]. Other nutrients and
104 heavy metals were determined by atomic absorption spectrometry (Vista Radial, Varian, Les Ulis,
105 France). The analyses were performed in triplicate.

106 2.4. *In vitro* test

107 Serial distilled water dilutions of each compost extract (1:10 w/v) and peat were plated in
108 nutrient agar (8 g L⁻¹ nutrient broth, (Scharlau, Spain); 15 g L⁻¹ technical agar (Scharlau, Spain)
109 amended with nystatin (50 mg L⁻¹) autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min, or sterilized streptomycin
110 (100 mg L⁻¹). A plug (5 mm) of a 7-day-old mycelium of FOM was placed in the center of the
111 petri dishes and incubated for 5 days at 28 C. The radial growth of FOM was measured after five
112 days of FOM growth in nutrient agar plates amended with the peat, GC and GCTh extracts. The
113 ability of composts to suppress the pathogen was calculated as the reduction of FOM growth
114 compared to the control (water amended plates). The analyses were performed in triplicate.

115 2.5. *In vivo* experiment

116 The experiment was carried out under greenhouse nursery conditions. Three treatments were
117 assayed: GC compost (GC-treatment), GCTh compost (GCTh-treatment) and peat
118 (peat-treatment) as growing media. Six polystyrene containers (10 wells per container) were
119 used for each treatment, and each container was considered as one unit. One muskmelon
120 (*Cucumis melo* L. cv. Giotto) seed was sown on each well and covered with vermiculite. Seeds
121 were germinated in a growth chamber at 28 ± 1 C and 90–95% relative humidity. After seeds
122 germinated, the different containers were randomly distributed in a polyethylene-covered
123 greenhouse under natural daylight conditions. Once the first true leaf appeared (15 days after
124 germination), three of the six containers for each treatment were inoculated on the substrate
125 with 2 mL of a FOM conidial suspension to achieve a final concentration of 10⁴ conidia g⁻¹
126 substrate. Control plants were inoculated with 2 mL of distilled water. Seedlings were irrigated
127 according to need and harvested 30 days after inoculation (D.A.I). The percentage of plants
128 infected by FOM was measured by accounting FOM on melon stem. FOM was isolated from
129 infected melon plants by cutting a piece from a melon stem (1 cm) and disinfecting it with

130 sodium hypochlorite (1%) for 5 min. Each sterilized surface plant piece was put on PDA dishes
131 and identified after 5 days at 28 C in darkness. Disease severity of Fusarium wilt was rated on a
132 scale of 1–4 (1. Healthy; 2. Yellowing; 3. Stem wilting; 4. Dead) based on Baayen and Van der
133 Plas [23].

134 *2.6. DNA extraction and PCR*

135 Total DNA was extracted from 250 mg compost samples using the Fast DNA kit for soil (Q-
136 Biogene, USA), following the modifications described by López-Mondéjar [24]. Samples were
137 previously ground with liquid nitrogen and kept at -20 C for DNA extraction. For the study of the
138 bacterial community, bacterial universal primers 338f and 907r [25] were used for partial
139 amplification of 16S RNA genes, obtaining a 570 bp final product. The PCR mixture (25 μ l)
140 contained a final concentration of 1x PCR buffer, 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ bovine serum albumin (BSA, 5 mg
141 mL⁻¹), 0.2 mM dNTPs mix, 0.2 μ M of each primer, 1 U of DNA polymerase (1 U IL-1, Biotools,
142 Spain), 20 mM tetramethylammonium chloride (TMA) and 1 μ l DNA. The thermal cycling
143 conditions consisted of an initial denaturation at 95 C for 3 min followed by 35 cycles of
144 denaturation at 95 C for 1 min, annealing at 57 C for 1 min, and elongation at 72 C for 1 min. A
145 final elongation was performed at 72 C for 10 min in a Takara PCR Thermal Cycler (Takara, Japan).
146 Products were checked by electrophoresis in 1.5% (w/v) agarose gel and ethidium bromide
147 staining (10 mg mL⁻¹). For the study of family 18 chitinolytic bacteria, degenerated PCR primers
148 GA1F/GA1R [26] targeted to a gene fragment from family 18 group A chitinases were used,
149 resulting in a 440 bp final product. The PCR mixture (25 μ l) contained a final concentration of 1x
150 PCR buffer, 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ BSA (5 mg mL⁻¹), 0.2 mM dNTPs mix, 0.2 μ M of each primer, 1 U of DNA
151 polymerase (1 U IL-1, Biotools, Spain), 0.1 μ M TMA and 100 ng μ l⁻¹ of extracted DNA. The thermal
152 cycling conditions consisted of an initial denaturation at 94 C for 5 min followed by 35 cycles of
153 denaturation at 94 C for 1 min, annealing at 60 C for 10 s and elongation at 72 C for 1 min. A
154 final elongation was performed at 72 C for 10 min in a Takara PCR Thermal Cycler (Takara, Japan)
155 [26]. Products were checked as previously described.

156 *2.7. T. harzianum T-78 quantification*

157 *T. harzianum* T-78 quantification was estimated in composts before setting up the experiments
158 by quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) in a total volume of 8 μ l using LightCycler™ (Roche Applied
159 Science, Germany), following the protocol described by López-Mondéjar [24]. The quantification
160 was performed in triplicate.

161 *2.8. Cloning and sequencing*

162 PCR products (three for each set of primers) of each compost sample were mixed and purified
163 using a QUIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Germany) following the manufacturer's
164 instructions. The purified products were cloned with the pCR II TAcloning kit for sequencing
165 (Invitrogen, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The appropriate presence of
166 inserts was determined by PCR with the primer sets 338f/907r and GA1F/GA1R, for the 16S rRNA
167 region and chitinase gene region respectively, and by electrophoresis in 1.5% (w/v) agarose gel
168 and ethidium bromide staining (10 mg mL⁻¹). Clone inserts were grouped according to their
169 restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) using four-base pair recognizing restriction
170 enzymes (HhaI and HaeIII), and representative clones containing different RFLP patterns were
171 sequenced using a 3730xl DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA). The obtained sequences
172 were checked by Chromas Lite 2.01 to eliminate primers and vector regions.

173 *2.9. Phylogenetic analysis of 16S rRNA and chitinase gene sequences*

174 Sequence identities of 16S rRNA were determined with the Ribosomal Database Project (RDP)
175 (<http://rdp.cme.msu.edu/>) [27]. The Bellerophon Chimera Check was used to determine
176 potential chimeric sequences [28]. The search for similar sequences was carried out with BLAST
177 (Basis Local Alignment Search Tool) (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BLAST>) in GenBank (NCBI
178 database, USA), and those found to be the most similar (at least 97% sequence similarity) were
179 used for the subsequent phylogenetic analysis. Sequences were aligned using ClustalW [29], and
180 phylogenetic trees were constructed using MEGA4 [30] by the neighbor-joining method [31]
181 based on the bootstrap analysis with a total of 1000 replicates [32]. For the analysis of the
182 chitinase gene, sequence identities were determined with BLAST as well as with similar
183 sequences previously deposited in the NCBI database (sequences displaying 78–99% identity
184 with previously identified chitinase genes). The phylogenetic analysis was performed as
185 described for 16S rRNA sequences.

186 The Shannon index ($H' = \sum p_i \times (\ln p_i)$) and Simpson index ($1 - D = 1 - [\sum n_i \times (n_i - 1)] / (N \times (N - 1))$)
187 were calculated to estimate the diversity of both samples. The relative abundances of bacterial
188 phyla were defined by calculating the number of sequenced clones from each phylum with
189 respect to the total sequences.

190 The 16S rRNA gene sequences have been deposited under accession number JQ736135–
191 JQ736244 in GenBank (NCBI database, USA). The chitinase gene sequences have been deposited
192 under accession numbers JQ906200–JQ906265 in GenBank (NCBI database,

193 USA).

194 *2.10. Statistical analysis*

195 Data were subjected to one-way ANOVA analysis. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS
196 19.0 software (SPSS Inc.). When the F-statistic was significant, Tukey's post hoc test ($P < 0.05$)
197 was used to separate means.

198 **3. Results**

199 *3.1. Compost characterization*

200 The main physico-chemical, chemical and microbiological characteristics of composts and peat
201 are shown in Table 1. Both pH and EC showed significant differences depending on the
202 treatment (Table 2). Peat showed the lowest values of pH and EC, while among composts, the
203 highest pH and CE was observed in compost without *T. harzianum* (GC). Composts showed
204 higher values of nutrient contents than peat (Table 1). Compost with *T. harzianum* (GCTh)
205 showed significant higher values of total N, K and Fe than compost without *T. harzianum* (GC),
206 while opposite results were observed for total C and P (Table 1 and 2). Compost CGTh showed
207 the presence of *T. harzianum* (10.42 log copies ITS g⁻¹), while compost GC and peat did not show
208 any copies of *T. harzianum*.

209 *3.2. In vitro test*

210 The percentage of inhibition of mycelial growth of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* (FOM) found in
211 selective media for fungi and bacteria was significantly influenced by treatments (Fig. 1, Table
212 2). In fungal culture media, growth inhibition of FOM reached values of 51% and 53% for GCTh
213 and CG respectively, compared to the growth inhibition of FOM for peat (20%). In bacterial
214 culture media, growth inhibition of FOM reached values of 59% and 54% in GCTh and GC
215 respectively, compared to the growth inhibition of FOM for peat (29%). Regardless of the media
216 used, no significant differences were observed in the inhibition of the growth of FOM with the
217 addition of *T. harzianum* to compost (GCTh) compared to GC (Fig. 1).

218 *3.3. In vivo experiment*

219 The percentage of stems infected by FOM was significantly influenced by treatment (Table 2).
220 Plants grown in GCTh-treatment showed the lowest percentage of stems infected by FOM,
221 reaching values of 10%, while the stem infection rate of plants grown in GC-treatment reached
222 25% and in peat-treatment 75% (Fig. 2A). Seedlings grown in both composts (GC-treatment and
223 GCTh-treatment) presented significantly lower disease severity compared to those grown in

224 peat-treatment. Disease severity values were 1.5 and 2.1 for GCTh-treatment and GC-treatment
225 respectively, while plants grown in peat-treatment showed a value of 3.0 (Fig. 2B).

226 3.4. 16S rRNA libraries

227 A preliminary study performed in triplicate of the bacterial community structures of composts
228 through denature gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE) showed changes in composts when *T.*
229 *harzianum* was added (data not shown). On the basis of the DGGE results, 16S rRNA gene clone
230 libraries from both composts (GCTh and GC) were constructed. A total of 192 clones were
231 randomly selected. Since identical RFLP profiles were obtained, a total of 125 clones were
232 sequenced.

233 One hundred and nineteen OTUs (sequence similarity 100%) over the region of the 16S rRNA
234 gene were identified in both composts and classified into seven phyla and a group of unclassified
235 bacteria (Fig. 3). Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria largely dominated the bacterial
236 communities of both composts. The GCTh clone library was classified into six phyla and a group
237 of unclassified bacteria. The largest phyla were Proteobacteria (48.7%) [alpha-Proteobacteria
238 (33.0%), delta-Proteobacteria (8.7%) and gamma-Proteobacteria (7.0%)], Actinobacteria
239 (19.1%) and Bacteroidetes (11.3%). The GC clone library was only classified into three phyla and
240 a group of unclassified bacteria. Among these phyla were Proteobacteria (41.2%) [alpha-
241 Proteobacteria (30.4%), beta-Proteobacteria (2.9%), delta-Proteobacteria (4.3%) and gamma-
242 Proteobacteria (2.9%)], Actinobacteria (30.4%) and Firmicutes (1.4%).

243 3.5. Chitinase gene libraries

244 Chitinase gene libraries were constructed to study the bacterial Family 18 subgroup A chitinase
245 gene diversity of both composts (Table 3). A total of 129 clones were selected randomly for RFLP.
246 Since few identical RFLP profiles were obtained 92 clones were sequenced. A total of 57 OTUs
247 (sequence similarity P99%) over the region of the chitinase gene were identified in both
248 composts. Sequences displayed 78–99% identity with previously identified chitinase genes and
249 were distributed into two different phyla, Actinobacteria (50.7%) and Proteobacteria (6.7%), and
250 a group of unclassified bacteria. The majority of chitinolytic Actinobacteria belonged to
251 *Streptomyces* spp. (53.8% and 32.3% in GCTh and GC respectively) along with species of
252 *Micromonospora* (11.9% in GCTh) and *Amycolaptosis* (10.2% in GCTh).

253 3.6. Diversity index

254 For 16S rRNA gene sequence and chitinase gene library analysis, diversity indices were
255 calculated according to phylum affiliation (Table 4). The diversity indices showed greater

256 diversity in GCTh than in GC. Analysis of the chitinase gene sequence library showed lower
257 diversity in GCTh than in GC.

258 **4. Discussion**

259 The amendment of a specific biological control agent (e.g. *T. harzianum*) to compost can lead to
260 a substrate with a broader –range suppressive effect [33] due to the mechanisms of action used
261 by this BCA [34], through changes in the biotic and abiotic substrate characteristics promoted
262 by the BCA [35], or through a combination of such mechanisms.

263 The biocontrol activity of composts analyzed through in vitro tests was different from that found
264 under in vivo conditions, although in both cases, composts showed higher biocontrol activity
265 than peat against FOM. This fact is in concordance with other studies in which composts
266 provided more successful disease suppression compared to peat [24,36,37]. No significant
267 differences in the inhibition of mycelial growth of FOM with non-amended and amended
268 compost with *T. harzianum* (GC, GCTh) were found. However, in vivo, the percentage of stems
269 infected by FOM and disease severity was significantly lower in the treatment amended with *T.*
270 *harzianum* (GCTh-treatment) than in the non-amended treatment (GC-treatment). Several
271 authors have pointed out the inability of in vitro assays to produce accurate solutions [4,38],
272 either due to the lack of interaction between plants, rhizosphere environment [38], the
273 interaction *Trichoderma*-plant [39] or the fact that it is difficult for many species of *Trichoderma*
274 to express fungal secondary metabolite genes under standard laboratory conditions [40]. These
275 findings highlight in vivo experiments are required to obtain accurate conclusions regarding the
276 suppression capacity of *Trichoderma*-amended composts.

277 From the point of view of fertility both compost showed some fertilizing value to be used as a
278 growing media [4,8], even GCTh showed higher values of N and P than GC. In this study, the
279 addition of *T. harzianum* to compost (GCTh) led to a significant decrease in pH and EC values
280 compared to results in GC. *Trichoderma* spp. produces organic acids, such as gluconic, citric or
281 fumaric acids, that decrease soil pH [34,35], promoting *T. harzianum* growth [41]. pH likely plays
282 a role, directly or indirectly, in the suppression of plant diseases through its impact on microbial
283 activity [42]. Specifically, the pH of growing media is a determinant of *Fusarium* wilt severity.
284 This fact is associated with the availability of macro- and micro-nutrients, which are important
285 for the growth, sporulation and virulence of *F. oxysporum* [43]. To give an example, high pH
286 values in certain composts achieve antifungal activity against *Fusarium* wilt in tomato and
287 carnation [44,45]. The analyzed composts attained high pH values, considered a positive

288 characteristic of organic amendments in terms of reducing diseases caused by *Fusarium* spp.
289 [43–45].

290 These high pH values reduce the availability of nutrients such as iron in organic growth media
291 [46], inducing siderophore production and competition for this mineral. This is a mechanism
292 used by *Trichoderma* spp. which results in explicit nutrient competition among microorganisms,
293 specifically against *F. oxysporum* [47,48]. Several authors have shown the importance of the
294 availability of specific nutrients for the biocontrol of *Fusarium* wilt induced by fluorescent
295 *Pseudomonas* spp., *T. harzianum* and *T. asperellum* as a result of iron competition [44,47,49,50].

296 In particular, we know that pH may strongly influence soil bacterial communities [51,52]. High
297 pH soils typically have higher relative abundances of Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes with
298 lower abundances of Acidobacteria compared with more acidic soils [53]. In our study, this
299 pattern holds in the case of Actinobacteria and Acidobacteria but not in the case of
300 Bacteroidetes. Rousk et al. [51] pointed out that the incremental differences in soil bacterial
301 community composition with pH were insignificant above pH 6.8. Factors other than pH may
302 also be driving the bacterial community patterns showed in Fig. 3. Changes in quantities of
303 organic carbon added to soil can have considerable influences on microbial communities. In this
304 sense, compost GCTh shows a lower C content as well as higher relative abundance of
305 Bacteroidetes and Proteobacteria groups, which have been putatively identified as being
306 copiotrophic taxa (those taxa that characteristically grow and multiply in high C environments).
307 Just as in the case of Bacteroidetes, the presence of *T. harzianum* in GCTh promoted the
308 appearance or increase of certain bacterial communities such as c-proteobacteria and
309 Verrumicrobia, all of them related to chitin-amended soils [54,55] (Fig. 3). The potential death
310 of part of the *T. harzianum* mycelia present in GCTh could imply an increase in chitin and
311 oligomers available in the medium [56] promoting the abundance of these groups despite the
312 lower C rate. The higher N content showed in GCTh could imply a higher relative abundance of
313 Proteobacteria spite of being identified as being copiotrophic taxa. A similar pattern has been
314 observed in other studies of microbial communities involving different levels of N amendments
315 on soil [57]. Conversely, oligotrophic microbes such as Acidobacteria, may be important
316 components in bacterial communities where C is limited as a result of low C flux or depletion of
317 C as a result of competition [58]. Thus, the presence of *T. harzianum* may create an oligotrophic
318 environment in compost as a function of competitive interactions. Moreover, the low levels of
319 easily biodegradable substances present in cellulose-enriched GCTh and GC composts may
320 enhance the competitiveness between microorganisms [56,59], maintaining both composts in a
321 competitive state [10]. These shifts in the composition of compost microbial communities

322 inoculated with *T. harzianum* are likely associated with shifts in the diversity of these
323 communities. The diversity indices that were influenced either by rare taxa, such as the Shannon
324 index H' , or by the most abundant taxa, such as the Simpson index ($1/D$) [60], showed greater
325 diversity in GCTh than in GC. As has been demonstrated previously [53,57], compost pH may be
326 responsible for the 16S bacterial community diversity. Other authors have also observed higher
327 microbial diversity after the addition of *T. harzianum* to soil [61].

328 Disease suppression by composts is mainly attributed to the biotic factor [6,62]. Analysis of 16S
329 rRNA clone libraries showed that phyla Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria dominated the
330 bacterial community in the composts. Several authors reported that the presence of
331 Actinobacteria is typical of suppressive composts as they may work as BCAs [63–65]. Thereby,
332 to understand the capacity of compost to suppress soil-borne plant diseases, it is important to
333 study chitinase genes [66]. Analysis of the chitinase gene composition was performed using a
334 set of primers developed based on a dataset biased in favor of the *Streptomyces* group. Some
335 species of *Streptomyces* are well-known for their ability to degrade the cell walls of soil-borne
336 plant fungi through the production of chitinases and antibiotics [66–68]. We therefore expected
337 the chitinase gene libraries of our composts to be dominated by Actinobacteria with species
338 related to *Streptomyces*. In the current study, the addition of *T. harzianum* to the GCTh compost
339 caused an increase in the relative abundance of species of *Streptomyces* spp., which is in
340 accordance with the increased suppression of FOM under in vivo conditions. The cell wall-
341 degrading enzymes of *T. harzianum* and *Streptomyces* spp. are produced during logarithmic
342 growth, and especially when the nutrient supply is limited [68]. The characteristics of the
343 growing media (vineyard pruning wastes) present in this study may benefit the growth of these
344 antifungal microbes more than it benefits FOM.

345 The loss of chitin gene diversity in GCTh might be due to the simultaneous presence of *T.*
346 *harzianum* and *Streptomyces*, since both efficiently compete with other microorganisms for
347 space and nutrients [69,70]. The competitiveness between antagonistic genera and microflora
348 of matured composts could be enhanced under low levels of easily biodegradable substances.

349 **5. Conclusions**

350 Vineyard pruning waste composts (GC and GCTh) are suitable to be used as suppressive growing
351 media against FOM. The incorporation of *T. harzianum* not only increased the biocontrol
352 capacity of this compost (GCTh) compared to GC, but also induced changes in the biotic and
353 abiotic characteristics of the compost. Changes in the physico-chemical characteristics of the
354 growing media could induce changes in bacterial community composition and increase the

355 relative abundance of species of *Streptomyces* spp. and therefore, the suppressiveness of GCTh
356 compost. These results should lay the groundwork to optimize the use of biological control
357 agents and appropriate source materials so as to achieve high levels of suppressiveness in
358 composts. In addition, the use of plant experiments is required to obtain realistic conclusions
359 concerning the suppression capacity of composts amended with *Trichoderma* species.

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363 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

364 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at
365 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2013.06.001>.

366 **References**

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